

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of some heterocyclic aldehydes by benzimidazolium fluorochromate in aqueous acetic acid medium

V. Saleem Malik^a, I. Vannamuthu^{a,b}, S. Syed Shafi^c and S. Sheik Mansoor^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, C. Abdul Hakeem College (Autonomous), Melvisharam-632 509, Tamilnadu, India
E-mail : smansoors2000@yahoo.co.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Periyar Government Arts College, Cuddalore-607 001, Tamilnadu, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Thiruvalluvar University, Serkadu, Vellore-632 106, Tamilnadu, India

Manuscript received online 19 November 2014, accepted 11 June 2016

Abstract : The oxidation of some heterocyclic aldehydes (HA) like 2-furaldehyde, 2-pyrrole-carbaldehyde and 2-thiophene-carbaldehyde by benzimidazolium fluorochromate (BIFC) have been studied in aqueous acetic acid medium. The oxidation leads to the formation of the corresponding carboxylic acids. The reaction is first order with respect to BIFC, heterocyclic aldehydes and [H⁺] and the reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions. The reaction has been studied in different percentage of acetic acid-water mixture. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords : Benzimidazolium fluorochromate, heterocyclic aldehydes, kinetics, oxidation.

Introduction

The search for new oxidizing agents is of interest to organic chemists. In recent years, many such reagents have been developed with some success. Some new Cr^{VI} based reagents like tetrabutylammonium bromochromate¹, tetraheptylammonium bromochromate², tripropylammonium fluorochromate³, tetraethylammonium bromochromate⁴, tetramethylammonium fluorochromate⁵, isoquinolinium bromochromate⁶, tetrahexylammonium bromochromate⁷ and imidazolium fluorochromate⁸ have been used to study the oxidation of various organic compounds.

Benzimidazolium fluorochromate is also one such oxidant developed recently⁹⁻¹⁴. It is a more efficient and stronger oxidizing agent. This new compound is more efficient for quantitative oxidation of several organic substrates and has certain advantages over similar oxidizing agents in terms of the amount of oxidant and solvent required, short reaction times and high yields.

A search of literature revealed that only few reports are available for kinetics of oxidation of heterocyclic aldehydes by various oxidizing agents¹⁵⁻²⁰. There seems to be no report on the kinetics of oxidation of heterocyclic

aldehydes by BIFC. In a continuation of our studies on the use of BIFC for the oxidation of various organic substrates¹¹⁻¹⁴, we report herein the kinetics of oxidation of 2-furaldehyde, 2-pyrrole-carbaldehyde and 2-thio-phene-carbaldehyde by benzimidazolium fluorochromate in aqueous acetic acid medium in the presence of perchloric acid.

Experimental

Materials : Benzimidazole and chromium trioxide were obtained from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). The heterocyclic aldehydes used were 2-furaldehyde (2-FA), 2-pyrrole-carbaldehyde (2-PA) and 2-thiophene-carbaldehyde (2-TA). Acetic acid was purified by standard method and the fraction distilling at 118 °C was collected.

Preparation of benzimidazolium fluorochromate : Benzimidazolium fluorochromate has been prepared from benzimidazole, 40% hydrofluoric acid and chromium trioxide in the molar ratio 1 : 1.3 : 1 at 0 °C. BIFC is obtained as yellow orange crystals. It is non-hygroscopic and light insensitive on storage⁹. The purity of BIFC was checked by the iodometric method. The purity is 99.8%. The yield of BIFC was 86%.

Kinetic measurements : The pseudo-first order conditions were attained by maintaining a large excess ($\times 15$ or more) of heterocyclic aldehydes over BIFC. The solvent was 50% acetic acid-50% water (v/v), unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed, at constant temperatures (± 0.01 K), by monitoring the decrease in [BIFC] spectrophotometrically at 368 nm using UV-Vis spectrophotometer, Shimadzu UV-1800 model. The pseudo-first order rate constant k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990$ to 0.999) plots of $\log [\text{BIFC}]$ against time for up to 80% reaction. The second order rate constant k_2 , was obtained from the relation $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{HA}]$.

Data analysis : Correlation analysis were carried out using Microcal origin (version 6) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using the correlation coefficient (r in the case of simple linear regression and R in the case of multiple linear regression) and standard deviation (SD).

Product analysis : Product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions i.e. with excess of the substrate over BIFC. In a typical experiment, 2-furaldehyde (0.1 mol), perchloric acid (0.24 mol) and BIFC (0.01 mol) were dissolved in acetic acid-water mixture (50%-50%) and the solution was allowed to stand in the dark for about 48 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The reaction mixture was then evaporated and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed with water many times. The ether layer was then kept on a water bath for the evaporation of ether and cooled in ice bath to obtain the product (m.p. 127–129 °C). The product was dissolved in benzene and a careful TLC analysis was done with furan-2-carboxylic acid and 2-furaldehyde as references. Only one spot corresponding to furan-2-carboxylic acid was obtained. Formation of furan-2-carboxylic acid was further confirmed by mixing the product with pure furan-2-carboxylic acid and noting that there was no change in the melting point. Similar experiments were conducted

for 2-pyrrole-carbaldehyde and 2-thiophene-carbaldehyde. The melting point obtained for furan-2-carboxylic acid (m.p. 127–129 °C; Lit. m.p. 128–132 °C), pyrrole-2-carboxylic acid (m.p. 206–208 °C; Lit. m.p. 204–208 °C) and thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (m.p. 124–126 °C; Lit. m.p. 125–127 °C) are in good agreement with literature.

FT-IR spectra were obtained as KBr discs on Shimadzu spectrometer. ^1H NMR (500 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz) spectra were obtained using Bruker DRX-500 Avance at ambient temperature, using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were determined on a Varion-Saturn 2000 GC/MS instrument. Elemental analysis were measured by means of Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN elemental analyzer flowchart.

(i) *2-Furan-carboxylic acid (from 2-furaldehyde) :*

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3014, 2866 (br, s, -OH), 1688 (s, C=O), 1464, 1017, 939, 784; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 12.3 (1H, s, COOH), 8.2 (1H, d, 5-H), 7.6 (1H, d, 3-H), 6.9 (1H, t, 4-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 112.8, 121.6, 145.4, 154.2, 177.9 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 97 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$) $^+$. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{O}_2$ (%) : C, 62.50; H, 4.20. Found : C, 62.44; H, 4.17.

(ii) *2-Pyrrole-carboxylic acid (from 2-pyrrole-carbaldehyde) :*

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3469 (-NH), 3022, 2844 (br, s, -OH), 1700 (s, C=O), 1540, 1112, 925, 778; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 12.2 (1H, s, COOH), 11.2 (1H, s, N-H), 7.3 (1H, d, 5-H), 7.2 (1H, d, 3-H), 6.2 (1H, t, 4-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 111.7, 122.2, 127.4, 134.0, 180.6 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 96 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$) $^+$. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NO}$ (%) : C, 63.50; H, 5.30; N, 14.73. Found : C, 63.40; H, 5.25; N, 14.

(iii) *2-Thiophene-carboxylic acid (from 2-thiophene-carbaldehyde) :*

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3087, 2884 (br, s, -OH), 1708 (s, C=O), 1526, 1117, 919, 762; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 12.6 (1H, s, COOH), 7.9 (1H, d, 5-H), 7.6 (1H, d, 3-H), 7.3 (1H, t, 4-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 128.4, 133.6, 134.2, 135.2, 166.7 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 113 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$) $^+$. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{OS}$ (%) : C, 53.55; H, 3.59. Found : C, 53.51; H, 3.56.

Stoichiometric studies : The stoichiometric studies for the oxidation of heterocyclic aldehydes by BIFC were carried out with oxidant in excess. The solvent composition 50% acetic acid-50% water (v/v) and $[H^+]$ were maintained as in the corresponding rate measurements. The temperature was maintained at 313 K. The heterocyclic aldehydes and BIFC were mixed in the ratio 1 : 4, 1 : 5, 1 : 6 and were allowed to react for 48 h at 313 K. The concentration of unreacted BIFC was determined. $\Delta[BIFC]$ was calculated. The stoichiometry was calculated from the ratio between $[HA]$ and $[BIFC]$. Stoichiometric analysis showed that 3 mol of aldehyde consumed 2 mol of BIFC in accordance with eq. (2) to give the corresponding carboxylic acid.

(2-Furaldehyde)

Results and discussion

The oxidation of some heterocyclic aldehydes (HA) like 2-furaldehyde, 2-pyrrole-carbaldehyde and 2-thiophene-carbaldehyde by BIFC have been conducted in 50% acetic acid and 50% water medium at 303 K, under pseudo-first order conditions and the result obtained were discussed in the following paragraphs.

Effect of varying BIFC concentration :

The concentration of BIFC was varied in the range of 0.5×10^{-3} to 2.5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ at constant $[HA]$, $[H^+]$ at 303 K and the rates were measured (Table 1). The near constancy in the value of k_{obs} irrespective of the concentration confirms the first order dependence on BIFC.

Effect of varying heterocyclic aldehyde concentration :

The concentration of the substrates 2-FA, 2-PA and 2-TA were varied in the range of 1.0×10^{-2} to 3.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ at 303 K and keeping all other reactant concentrations as constant and the rates were measured (Table 1). The rate of oxidation increased progressively on increasing the concentration of heterocyclic aldehydes. The plot of $\log k_{obs}$ versus $\log [HA]$ gave the slope of 1.06, 0.97 and 1.04 respectively for 2-FA, 2-PA and 2-TA respectively (Fig. 1). Under pseudo-first order conditions, the plot of k_{obs} versus $[HA]$ is linear passing through origin (Fig. 2). These results confirm the first order nature of the reaction with respect to $[HA]$.

Table 1. Effect of variation of $[HA]$, $[BIFC]$ and $[H^+]$ on the rate of the reaction at 303 K^{a,b}

$10^3 [BIFC]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^2 [HA]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[H^+]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)		
			2-FA	2-PA	2-TA
0.5	2.0	0.32	6.08	4.40	3.06
1.0	2.0	0.32	6.12	4.46	3.14
1.5	2.0	0.32	6.18	4.44	3.16
2.0	2.0	0.32	6.20	4.50	3.18
2.5	2.0	0.32	6.06	4.48	3.10
1.0	1.0	0.32	2.28	2.26	1.46
1.0	1.5	0.32	4.40	3.40	2.30
1.0	2.5	0.32	7.66	5.50	3.80
1.0	3.0	0.32	9.26	6.60	4.62
1.0	2.0	0.16	3.02	2.12	1.50
1.0	2.0	0.24	4.56	3.24	2.32
1.0	2.0	0.40	7.52	5.54	3.78
1.0	2.0	0.48	9.08	6.66	4.62

^aAs determined by spectrophotometrically following the disappearance of Cr^{VI} at 368 nm; the error quoted in k values is the 95% confidence limit of 'Student t test'.

^bEstimated from pseudo-first order plots over 80% reaction.

Solvent composition = 50% AcOH-50% H₂O (v/v).

Fig. 1. Showing order plot of heterocyclic aldehydes for the oxidation of heterocyclic aldehydes by BIFC.

Effect of varying perchloric acid concentration :

Perchloric acid has been used as a source of H^+ in reaction medium. The concentration of H^+ was varied in the range 0.16 to 0.48 mol dm⁻³ keeping all other reactant concentration as constant at 303 K and the rates were measured (Table 1). The acid catalysed nature of this oxidation is confirmed by an increase in the rate on the

Fig. 2. Showing direct plot of heterocyclic aldehydes for the oxidation of heterocyclic aldehydes by BIFC.

addition of H^+ . The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\log [H^+]$ is a straight line with the slope of 1.01, 1.05 and 1.06 respectively for 2-FA, 2-PA and 2-TA respectively. Therefore, order with respect to H^+ is one for 2-FA, 2-PA and 2-TA respectively. BIFC may become protonated in the presence of acid and the protonated BIFC may function as an effective oxidant.

Effect of acidity :

The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions (Table 1). The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of BIFC to give a stronger oxidant and electrophile.

The formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PCC²¹ and PFC²².

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile :

The possibility of radical formation and its involvement in the reaction has been ruled out as the addition of acrylonitrile in the reaction mixture developed no turbidity and hence the reaction rates was not affected even the [acrylonitrile] was at 1.0×10^{-3} to 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} (Table 2). Thus, a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals is unlikely.

Effect of varying ionic strength of reaction rate :

The effect of ionic strength was studied by varying the $NaClO_4$ concentration in the reaction medium. The

Table 2. Effect of acrylonitrile (AN) and $NaClO_4$ on the oxidation of heterocyclic aldehydes by BIFC at 303 K

10^3 [AN] (mol dm^{-3})	10^3 [$NaClO_4$] (mol dm^{-3})	$10^4 k_1$ (s^{-1})		
		2-FA	2-PA	2-TA
0.0	0.0	6.12	4.46	3.14
1.0	0.0	6.16	4.48	3.16
2.0	0.0	6.10	4.44	3.14
3.0	0.0	6.22	4.39	3.18
4.0	0.0	6.20	4.40	3.20
5.0	0.0	6.16	4.50	3.16
0.0	1.0	6.09	4.52	3.10
0.0	2.0	6.07	4.44	3.10
0.0	3.0	6.11	4.43	3.22
0.0	4.0	6.19	4.42	3.15
0.0	5.0	6.20	4.39	3.18

10^2 [HA] = 2.0 mol dm^{-3} ; 10^3 [BIFC] = 1.0 mol dm^{-3} ; 10 [H^+] = 3.2 mol dm^{-3} .

Solvent composition = 50% AcOH-50% H_2O (v/v).

ionic strength of the reaction medium was varied from 1.0×10^{-3} to 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} and keeping all other reactant concentration as constant. It was found that the values of the rate constants at different ionic strength of the reaction medium has no significant effect on the reaction rate (Table 2).

Effect of solvent polarity on reaction rate :

The oxidation of heterocyclic aldehydes have been studied in the binary mixture of acetic acid and water as the solvent medium. For the oxidation of all heterocyclic aldehydes, the reaction rate increased remarkably with the increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the solvent medium. These results are presented in Table 3.

The effect from solvent composition on the reaction rate was studied by varying the concentration of acetic acid from 30% to 70%. The pseudo-first order rate constants were estimated for the oxidation of hydroxy acids, with BIFC in the presence of perchloric acid at a constant ionic strength. The reaction rate is increases markedly with the increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the medium (Table 3). When the acid content increases in the medium, the acidity of the medium is increased whereas the dielectric constant of the medium is decreased. These two effects cause the rate of the oxidation to increase markedly.

The enhancement of the reaction rate with an increase

Table 3. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the oxidation of 2-furaldehyde, 2-pyrrole-carbaldehyde and 2-thiophene-carbaldehyde by BIFC at various percentage of acetic acid-water medium at various temperatures

%AcOH- H ₂ O (v/v)	Dielectric constant	10 ⁴ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)			
		298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
2-Furaldehyde					
30-70	72.0	3.46	4.60	6.00	7.88
40-60	63.3	4.08	5.44	7.22	9.62
50-50	56.0	4.52	6.12	8.14	11.00
60-40	45.5	6.06	8.16	11.10	15.22
70-30	38.5	7.08	9.60	13.32	18.50
2-Pyrrole-carbaldehyde					
30-70	72.0	2.30	3.40	4.72	6.68
40-60	63.3	2.76	3.98	5.72	8.22
50-50	56.0	3.02	4.46	6.16	8.88
60-40	45.5	4.06	5.88	8.26	11.76
70-30	38.5	4.80	7.04	10.22	14.96
2-Thiophene-carbaldehyde					
30-70	72.0	1.52	2.32	3.50	5.36
40-60	63.3	1.80	2.78	4.06	6.02
50-50	56.0	2.02	3.14	4.66	7.06
60-40	45.5	2.60	4.06	6.08	9.12
70-30	38.5	3.30	4.78	7.10	10.56

10² [HA] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [BIFC] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³; 10 [H⁺] = 3.2 mol dm⁻³.

in the amount of acetic acid generally may be attributed to two factors, viz. (i) the increase in acidity occurring at constant [H⁺] and (ii) the decrease in the dielectric constant with an increase in the acetic acid content.

The plot of log k₁ versus 1/D (dielectric constant) is linear with positive slope suggesting the presence of either dipole-dipole or ion-dipole type of interaction between the oxidant and the substrate^{23,24} (Fig. 2). Plot of log k₁ versus (D - 1)/(2D + 1) is a curvature indicating the absence of dipole-dipole interaction in the rate determining step.

Amis (1967) holds the view that in an ion-dipole reaction involving a positive ionic reactant, the rate would decrease with increasing dielectric constant of the medium and if the reactant were to be a negatively charged ion, the rate would increase with the increasing dielectric constant. In this case there is a possibility of a positive ionic reactant, as the rate decreases with the increasing

Fig. 3. Plot of 1/D against log k_{obs} showing effect of solvent polarity for the oxidation of heterocyclic aldehydes by BIFC.

dielectric constant of the medium²⁶. Due to the polar nature of the solvent, transition state is stabilized, i.e. the polar solvent molecules surround the transition state and result in less disproportion.

Thermodynamic parameters :

The kinetics of oxidation of heterocyclic aldehydes were studied at four different temperatures viz. 298, 303, 308 and 313 K. The second order rate constants were calculated (Table 4). The Arrhenius plot of log k₂ versus 1/T is found to be linear. The enthalpy of activation, entropy of activation and free energy of activation were calculated from k₂ at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K using the Eyring relationship by the method of least square and presented in Table 4. The entropy of activation is negative for heterocyclic aldehydes.

Isokinetic relationship :

The reaction is neither isoenthalpic nor isoentropic but complies with the compensation law also known as the isokinetic relationship.

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H^\circ + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger \quad (4)$$

The isokinetic temperature β is the temperature at which all the compounds of the series react equally fast. Also, at the isokinetic temperature, the variation of substituent has no influence on the free energy of activation. Exner suggested a method of testing the validity of isokinetic relationship²⁷. The isokinetic relationship is tested by plotting the logarithms of rate constants at two different tem-

Table 4. Second order rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of 2-furaldehyde, 2-pyrrole-carbaldehyde and 2-thiophene-carbaldehyde by BIFC at various percentage of acetic acid-water medium

%AcOH- H ₂ O (v/v)	10 ³ k ₂ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				E _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-ΔS [#] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG [#] (kJmol ⁻¹) (at 303 K)
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K				
2-Furaldehyde								
30-70	1.73	2.30	3.00	3.94	41.26	151.04±2.4	37.90±0.8	83.67±1.5
40-60	2.04	2.72	3.61	4.81	43.08	140.89±0.3	40.59±0.1	83.27±0.2
50-50	2.26	3.06	4.07	5.50	44.42	135.15±0.6	42.12±0.2	83.07±0.4
60-40	3.03	4.08	5.55	7.61	46.14	126.92±1.2	43.84±0.4	82.29±0.8
70-30	3.54	4.80	6.66	9.25	48.33	118.62±2.1	45.95±0.7	81.91±1.4
2-Pyrrole-carbaldehyde								
30-70	1.15	1.70	2.36	3.34	53.22	111.60±3.3	50.74±1.1	84.55±2.0
40-60	1.38	1.99	2.86	4.11	55.33	104.70±0.6	52.46±0.2	84.18±0.4
50-50	1.51	2.23	3.08	4.44	53.60	107.96±3.3	51.31±1.1	84.02±2.2
60-40	2.03	2.94	4.13	5.88	53.22	106.82±1.2	48.16±0.4	80.52±0.8
70-30	2.40	3.52	5.11	7.48	57.06	99.64±0.3	54.56±0.1	84.75±0.2
2-Thiophene-carbaldehyde								
30-70	0.76	1.16	1.75	2.68	63.18	81.54±0.3	60.69±0.1	85.40±0.2
40-60	0.90	1.38	2.03	3.01	60.31	89.39±2.1	58.02±0.7	85.10±1.4
50-50	1.01	1.57	2.33	3.53	62.61	81.35±2.4	60.12±0.8	84.76±1.6
60-40	1.30	2.03	3.04	4.56	63.00	76.95±3.0	60.88±1.0	84.20±2.0
70-30	1.65	2.39	3.55	5.28	58.58	90.73±2.7	56.09±0.9	83.58±1.8

10² [HA] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [BIFC] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³; 10 [H⁺] = 3.2 mol dm⁻³.

peratures ($T_2 > T_1$) against each other according to eq. (5).

$$\log k \text{ (at } T_2) = a + b \log k \text{ (at } T_1) \quad (5)$$

The linear relationship in Exner plots at $4 + \log k_2$ (303 K) and $4 + \log k_2$ (308 K) observed in the present study imply the validity of the isokinetic relationship^{27,28}. Isokinetic temperature obtained is 542 ± 7 K. The linear isokinetic correlation implies that 2-FA, 2-PA and 2-TA are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in the rate are governed by the changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of activation²⁹.

Mechanism of oxidation :

A mechanism leading to the formation of the free radicals is unlikely in view of the failure to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile and no effect of the radical scavenger on the reaction rate. Positive slope of $\log k_1$ versus $1/D$ plot indicates that the reaction involves a cation-dipole type of interaction in the rate determining step. The linear isokinetic correlation implies that 2-furaldehyde,

2-pyrrole-carbaldehyde and 2-thiophene-carbaldehyde are oxidized by the same mechanism.

It has been shown that aldehyde oxidation reactions proceeded via the hydrated form³⁰⁻³³. Hence, a mechanism involving a direct hydrogen-transfer reaction between a free aldehyde and BIFC was very unlikely. In the case of heteroaldehydes, the heteroatoms are strong resonance donors in these five-membered ring systems. The observed order of reactivity in the present study was : 2-furaldehyde > 2-pyrrole-carbaldehyde > 2-thiophene-carbaldehyde (Table 1), which was in conformity with the decreasing electronegativities of O, N and S atoms (electronegativities were : O, 3.50; N, 3.07; S, 2.44)³⁴. The inference was that electronegative substituents increased the oxidation rates by increasing the equilibrium concentrations of the intermediate chromate ester of the aldehyde hydrate.

The close resemblance in the structures of aldehyde hydrates and alcohols would favor similar pathways in their oxidation processes. The oxidation of alcohols had

demonstrated the rate-determining decomposition of the protonated acid chromate ester³⁵. In an analogous manner, the oxidation of aldehydes could be visualized as proceeding via the formation of a similar intermediate (an ester of the aldehyde hydrate). If the chromium was coordinated through the -OH group (of the aldehyde hydrate) in the cyclic transition state^{36,37} this would facilitate the formation of the chromate ester and enhance the ease of its oxidation to the corresponding carboxylic acid. Such a transition state envisaged the transfer of electrons towards the chromium, occurring by the formation of the carbon-hydrogen-oxygen bonds, as well as by the carbon-oxygen-chromium bonds.

The slow step of the reaction involved the participation of the aldehyde hydrate, protonated BIFC and two

electrons in a cyclic system. Removal of the hydrogen (on the carbon) was part of this step. Since the five-membered heterocyclic ring system was a planar pentagon with sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms and possessed considerable aromatic character arising from delocalization of the two paired electrons, it would undergo a reaction via an electrocyclic mechanism involving six electrons, being a Hückel-type system ($4n + 2$), this was an allowed process³⁸.

The sequence of reactions for the oxidation of heteroaldehydes by BIFCH⁺, in acid medium (Scheme 1) showed that BIFC was converted to the protonated BIFC i.e. BIFCH⁺. The substrate (A) was converted to the hydrated form (Hy), which reacted with BIFCH⁺, giving the monochromate ester intermediate (E). The

Scheme 1. Mechanism of oxidation of heterocyclic aldehydes by BIFC.

monochromate ester (E) underwent decomposition, in the rate determining step, to give the product (the corresponding acid), along with the Cr^{IV} species.

Conclusions

The kinetics of oxidation of heterocyclic aldehydes has been investigated in aqueous acetic acid medium in the presence of perchloric acid by spectrophotometrically at 303 K. The oxidation of heterocyclic aldehydes by BIFC is first order each with respect to the heterocyclic aldehydes, BIFC and hydrogen ion. The oxidation is catalysed by perchloric acid. The lowering of dielectric constant of reaction medium increases the reaction rate significantly. The reaction does not show the polymerization, which indicates the absence of free radical intermediate in the oxidation. In the present study the observed order of reactivity was : 2-furaldehyde > 2-pyrrole-carbaldehyde > 2-thiophene-carbaldehyde.

References

- S. Ghammamy, K. Mehrani, H. Afrand and M. Hajighahrammani, *Afr. J. Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2007, **1**, 8.
- S. Ghammamy, K. Mehrani, H. Afrand, Z. Javanshir, G. Rezaeibehbahani, A. Moghimi and Z. S. Aghbolagh, *J. Chil. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **54**, 491.
- S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *J. Mole. Liq.*, 2010, **155**, 85.
- S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 2011, **225**, 249.
- B. Sadeghy and S. Ghammami, *Russ. J. Gen. Chem.*, 2005, **75**, 1886.
- S. B. Patwari, S. V. Khansole and Y. B. Vibhute, *J. Iran Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **6**, 399.
- S. S. Mansoor and B. H. Asghar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2013, **90**, 1395.
- S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **89**, 69.
- V. Sivamurugan, G. A. Rajkumar, B. Arabindoo and V. Murugesan, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2005, **44A**, 144.
- J. Dharmaraja, K. Krishnasamy and M. Shanmugam, *E-J. Chem.*, 2008, **5**, 754.
- S. S. Mansoor, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2010, **22**, 7591.
- S. S. Mansoor, S. S. Shafi and S. Z. Ahmed, *Arab. J. Chem.*, doi:10.1016/j.arabjc.2011.06.026.
- S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *Arab. J. Chem.*, 2014, **7**, 171.
- B. H. Asghar, S. S. Mansoor, A. M. Hussain, V. S. Malik, K. Aswin and S. P. N. Sudhan, *Arab. J. Chem.*, doi: http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2013.07.043.
- G. S. Chaubey, S. Das and M. K. Mahanti, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2002, **75**, 2215.
- G. S. Chaubey and Bansie, *J. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 2004, **17**, 83.
- P. Radhasyam and R. M. Puma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 491.
- D. Kumar, A. Rani, D. S. N. Prasad and K. S. Gupta, *Reac. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1991, **43**, 133.
- V. S. Kumar, M. Rukmangantham and B. Ramkumar, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2011, **23**, 925.
- H. Saunte, G. S. Chaubey and M. K. Mahanti, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 2010, **83**, 291.
- V. Sharma, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 607.
- V. Sharma, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1996, 290.
- G. J. Scatchard, *Chem. Phys.*, 1932, **10**, 229.
- G. J. Scatchard, *Chem. Phys.*, 1939, **7**, 657.
- E. S. Amis, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic Press, New York, 1967, 42.
- D. S. Bhuvaneshwari and K. P. Elango, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2007, **39**, 657.
- O. Exner, *Nature*, 1964, 488.
- O. Exner, J. R. Streitwiser and R. W. Talt, "Progress in Physical Organic Chemistry", John Wiley, New York, 1973, 41.
- J. F. Leffler and E. Grunwald, "Rates and Equilibrium of Organic Reactions", Wiley, New York, 1963.
- A. L. Jain and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Res. (M)*, 1983, 678.
- K. K. Banerji, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, **43**, 5949.
- V. K. Sharma, K. Sharma and N. Mishra, *Oxid. Commun.*, 1993, **16**, 33.
- H. A. A. Medien, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 2003, **58b**, 1201.
- F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1985, p. 115.
- J. Rocek, F. H. Westheimer, A. Eschenmoser, L. Moldovanyi and J. Schreiber, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1962, **45**, 2554.
- U. Klanning, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1958, **12**, 576.
- C. G. Swain, R. F. W. Bader, R. M. Estene and R. N. Griffin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1951.
- J. S. Littler, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, **27**, 81.